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Prof. M.O.B. Mohammed

*Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education,
Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos Nigeria*

Email: mubashiru.mohammed@lasu.edu.ng

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Email: goduro@ucc.edu.gh*

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FREE EDUCATION PROGRAM IN SUB SAHARAN AFRICA: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SIERRA LEONE AND NIGERIA

James VIBBI

Produce Monitoring Board, Sierra Leone
Email: jvibbi@producemonitoringboard.sl
Phone: +23278762040

Abidat Oluwashola MOHAMMED

Department of Language, Arts and Social Science Education,
Faculty of Education, Lagos State University, Nigeria.
Email: abidat.mohammed@lasu.edu.ng
Phone: +2348028323225

Abstract

This paper compared the efficacy of free education programs in Sub-Saharan Africa, with a focus on the Free Quality School Education (FQSE) of Sierra Leone and Universal Basic Education (UBE) of Nigeria. First, the paper observed the current educational system in Sub-Saharan Africa and its performance relative to the rest of the world. Second, an analysis of the free education programs in each of the two countries is conducted, looking at components such as inception, vision, mission, aims/objectives, scope, duration, progress, and challenges. Third, the paper evaluated the performance of these programs in terms of improved access to education and reduced school drop-out rates. The paper found that both Nigeria and Sierra Leone have implemented free education programs in recent years, and both countries have seen positive results in terms of increased access to education and reduced drop-out rates. However, in Nigeria, the free education program is limited in scope and is hindered by political and financial challenges. In contrast, Sierra Leone has seen greater success in the program and is making strides in increasing access and reducing drop-out rates. Overall, the paper highlights the importance of free education programs in Sub-Saharan Africa, and highlights the challenges faced in implementing such programs in Sierra Leone and Nigeria. It concludes that these programs are important for improving access to education and reducing school drop-out rates, and suggests further research into the efficacy and challenges of such programs. To this end, the study recommended that the two countries should discover the synergies between the aspects of the free education policies that have worked overtime to improve the operations of the policies in the two countries and Africa at large.

Keywords: Free Education Program, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Sub-Saharan Africa

1. Introduction

The right to education is paramount on the agenda of the United Nations because it is the vehicle for transforming and transmitting societal values from one generation to another. A nation's economic prospect follows the learning curve of its children because what a nation wants to be, socially, technologically, and politically, is largely determined by the kind of education she offers to her citizens. This realization is exemplified in the international goals, strategies and targets that have been set in the past decades through international fora and agendas, such as Education for All (EFA), the World Education Forum in Dakar, Senegal in 2000 and the Millennium Development Goals ratified by the world's leaders and other stakeholders at the turn of the century. Three agencies; the World Bank, the United Nations

Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), and the United Nations International Children Funds (UNICEF) came together to sponsor the World Conference on Education at Jomtien, Thailand in 1990 with representatives from over 150 countries including Sierra-Leone and Nigeria (Odusanya, 2017).

The highlight of the World Declaration on Education for All (EFA) among other things is that - "satisfying basic learning needs requires an expanded vision which encompasses universalizing access and promoting equity, focusing on learning, broadening the means and scope of basic education, enhancing the environment for learning and strengthening partnership (World Conference on Education for All in Odusanya, 2017). These assumptions may have formed the springboard for the Universal Basic Education (UBE) in Nigeria formed in 1999 and probably the Free Quality School Education (FQSE) later formed in 2018. However, both programs are situated within the large context of a global quest for Education for All, and they both have one fundamental principle in common; that everybody must have opportunity to equivalent education irrespective of gender, social, physical, and economic conditions. Specifically, the six goals of EFA are early childhood care and education, universal primary education, learning skills for young people; adult literacy; gender parity and equality; and qualitative education (Odusanya, 2017).

However, the progress has not been even across several countries during the last several decades. While some developing countries have made rapid progress and today are in the forefront with respect to primary education and achievement of other EFA goals, with nearly one hundred percent enrolment ratios, high completion rates, gender parity, etc., there are several countries which lag far behind. Among the world regions, Sub-Saharan Africa such as Sierra Leone and Nigeria seem to belong to the latter category (Kamara, 2020; Odusanya, 2017; Tilak, 2009). This paper, therefore, compares free education programs in Sub Sahara Africa such as Nigeria and Sierra Leone. The concept of the comparison indicates a process of studying two or more things to see how they are alike or different (Kubow & Fossum, 2007). The concern of comparative educators, therefore, includes identifying peculiar cultural values when analysing national data; progress made in education and notable pitfalls to avoid. Cross-national comparisons have served increasingly as a means of gaining a better understanding of different societies, their structures, and institutions (Macfarlane, 2004). This paper, therefore, sought to examine the similarities, differences, progress, and challenges in the free education policies of Nigeria and Sierra Leone.

2. Concept of Free Quality School Education (FQSE) in Sierra Leone

FQSE is a new system of education introduced in August 2018 by His Excellency, President Retired Brigadier-General Julius Maada Bio in Sierra Leone. The FQSE program is dedicated to the promotion of quality education in Sierra Leone (Vibbi & Mohammed, 2023). Quality education is one that focuses on the whole child-the social, emotional, mental, physical, and cognitive development of each student regardless of gender, race, ethnicity, socio-economic status, or geographic location. It prepares the child for life, not just for testing (UNITE For Quality Education, 2020).

The objective of FQSE is therefore to increase nationwide access to pre-primary, primary and secondary schools as well as school-level technical and vocational education and training. The goal is that all children will be able to complete basic education and be prepared to move on to pursue higher education and training as appropriate needed for the workforce for national development. FQSE ensures that all the core costs for formal and non-formal

school education are covered by the government of Sierra Leone and requires parents to take responsibility for the ancillary costs according to the ability to pay (Kamara, 2020).

FQSE ensures that the Government provides learning materials such as text and exercise books to all pupils, and teaching materials to all teachers. Also, the Government will pay school fees, and subsidization of fees to all school heads of Government and Government-assisted schools for the provision of furniture, expansion of school infrastructure, and school amenities like water and sanitation facilities. The government also ensures the Recruitment of additional teachers to improve learning outcomes and school feeding for pupils in hard-to-reach communities across Sierra Leone. The FQSE program has six components which are as follows: access, equity, completion, quality assurance and relevance, integrity, and system strengthening in the nation.

3. Concept of Universal Basic Education (UBE) in Nigeria

UBE in Nigeria is a nine (9) year basic educational program launched on the 30th September, 1999 in Sokoto, Sokoto State by the Federal Republic of Nigeria to eradicate illiteracy, ignorance and poverty. It was aimed as a stimulant to accelerate national development, political consciousness, and national integration. Former President of Nigeria, Olusegun Obasanjo flagged UBE in Sokoto, Sokoto State as a strategy for the achievement of Education for All (EFA) and the education-related Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). The UBE bill was signed into law by former President Obasanjo after its passage by the National Assembly on 26th May 2004. The UBEA Act makes provision for basic education comprising Early Child Care Education (ECCE), Primary and Junior Secondary Education (Ordui & Nwamadi-Wosu, 2019). Then there is also the non-formal program which is set to take care of those who dropped out of school (Ordui & Nwamadi-Wosu, 2019; Aboluwodi, 2015).

Universal Basic Education is defined as a base-level education that is designed to satisfy at least the minimum learning needs of individuals. Furthermore, it was pointed out that this kind of education is the foundation for sustainable life-long learning (Doggoh, 2014). Amadi and Wodi (2020) defined UBE as “early childhood care for education comprising of the nine years of formal schooling, adult literacy and non-formal program and the education of special groups such as nomads, migrants, girl child and women, street children and disabled groups.

Ogunsanmi and Ibimiluyi (2014) posited that since the introduction of Western form of education in Nigeria, various policies and programs have been initiated and executed for the sake of providing education to as many that are willing and ready to consume it for personal as well as socio-political development. Such programs include the adoption of Universal Primary Education (UPE) in 1976 and the introduction of Universal Basic Education (UBE) in 1999 with the major aim of providing basic educational skills for children and all citizens to be useful to their communities, society and the world at large.

UBE program provides basic education. Basic education, in this respect, involves the provision of infrastructure, continuous and sustainable in-service training for teachers and giving prominence to skills acquisition in primary and secondary education. It ensures that the basic learning needs of children and adolescents are met (Aboluwodi, 2015). Basic education as a process encourages close articulation of formal, non-formal and informal approaches to education and structures for the awakening of all-round developments of human and capital potentials (Ogunniran, Isuku & Hou, 2019).

4. Comparison of Free Quality School Education (FQSE) in Sierra Leone and Universal Basic Education (UBE) in Nigeria

This section evaluates the free education programme in Sierra Leone and Nigeria in terms of the inception of the programme in the two countries, the objectives, vision, mission, goals/objectives, progress as well as challenges.

a) The Inception, Rationale and Vision

Table 1: Comparison of the Inception, Rationale and Vision of FQSE and UBE

S/N	Concepts	Free Quality School Education (FQSE)	Universal Basic Education (UBE)
1	Inception	It is a new system of education introduced in August 2018 by His Excellency, President Retired Brigadier-General Julius Maada Bio in Sierra Leone	It is a program launched on the 30th of September 1999 in Sokoto, Sokoto State by the Federal Republic of Nigeria - Former President Olusegun Obasanjo
2	Rationale	FQSE was launched because of the constant and rampant frequency of massive failure and the poor standard of education in the country that has led to war, corruption, lawlessness behaviour; underdevelopment and backwardness	UBE was launched because of the high rate of illiteracy, ignorance and poverty among the citizens and to improve on the former UPE program
3	Vision	To provide free and compulsory quality education that focuses on the whole child - the social, emotional, mental, physical, and cognitive development of each student regardless of gender, race, ethnicity, socio-economic status, or geographic location	To provide free and compulsory basic education that ensure nine years of continuous education, in which every child should acquire appropriate and relevant skills and values and be employable in order to contribute his or her quota to National Development

Source: Kamara, 2020; (UNITE For Quality Education, 2020; Ordui and Nwamadi-Wosu, 2019; Aboluwodi, 2015

Table 1 showed that the Universal Basic Education program in Nigeria started earlier than the Free Quality School Education in Sierra Leone. UBE started in September 1999 whereas FQSE was launched in 2018. The late start of Free Quality School Education in Sierra Leone maybe due to corruption and inadequacy of funds. However, both programs were started by the federal government which is a good gesture.

The rationale behind the commencement of FQSE differs from that of UBE. FQSE was started because of rampant increase in massive failure and the poor standard of education in the country that resulted to war, corruption, lawless behaviours, and underdevelopment. However, UBE began not only as a result of the high rate of illiteracy, ignorance and poverty but because of the numerous challenges experienced in the former UPE program. Prior to the introduction of the UBE program, the existing policy and program of government for education (UPE) were found to give rise to distortions, a high rate of dropouts, narrow curriculum content and half-baked graduates that did not meet the needs of the society. The UBE scheme was therefore launched to arrest the decline and decay as well as expand and

improve on the UPE scheme, therefore, ensuring free access to education, reducing the rate of dropout to the minimum, making education relevant to the needs of learners and a lifelong enterprise (Aboluwodi, 2015).

The vision of FQSE and UBE are quite similar in that they both provide free and compulsory education for children. Therefore, parents are mandated to take their children/wards to school. Both programs stipulate severe penalties/punishments for parents or guardians who fail to bring their wards to school. However, their vision slightly differs in that the vision of FQSE focuses on “providing quality education that involves the social, emotional, mental, physical, and cognitive development of the whole child” while that of UBE focuses on providing nine years of basic education that ensures the acquisition of appropriate and relevant skills, and values by the child.

b) The Scope and Duration

Table 2: Comparison of the Scope and Duration of FQSE and UBE

S/N	Concepts	Free Quality School Education (FQSE)	Universal Basic Education (UBE)
1	Scope	Pre-primary, primary, junior, and senior secondary school levels. Also, technical and vocational education and training	Early Child Care Education (ECCE), Primary and Junior Secondary Education. Also, non-formal program to take care of those who dropped out of school
2	Duration	12 years duration comprising of 6 years primary, 3 years junior secondary and 3 years senior secondary school education	9 years duration, comprising 6 years of primary education and 3 years of junior secondary education. (Federal Government of Nigeria in

Source: MBBSE, 2021; Kamara, 2020; Ordui & Nwamadi-Wosu, 2019; UBEC, 2012

In scope, FQSE involves the pre-primary and primary school levels (6 years), junior (3 years) and senior secondary (3 years) school levels. It also comprises of technical and vocational education and training for the children. However, that of UBE involves only Early Child Care Education (ECCE) and Primary school levels (6 years), and Junior Secondary Education (3 years). It also comprises of a non-formal program to take care of those who dropped out of school. While the duration of FQSE is 12 years, that of UBE is 9 years. FQSE involves both junior and senior secondary school education while UBE involves only junior secondary school education.

Table 3: Comparison of the Mission of FQSE and UBE

Free Quality School Education (FQSE)	Universal Basic Education (UBE)
i. Strictly meant for children between the ages of three and eighteen years;	1) Strictly meant for children between the ages of six and fifteen years
ii. Non-payment of school fees by parents and guardians;	2) Parents to take responsibility for the ancillary costs;
iii. Parents to take responsibility for the ancillary costs according to the ability to pay;	3) Public enlightenment and social mobilization for full community involvement;
iv. Provision of teaching and learning materials by the Government;	4) Data collection and analysis; Planning, monitoring and evaluation;

v. Recruitment of additional teachers to improve learning outcomes;	5) Teachers: their recruitment, education, training, retraining, motivation, etc;
vi. Payment of examination fees for pupils taking public exams (NPSE, BECE and WASSCE);	6) Provision of infrastructural facilities;
vii. School feeding for pupils in hard-to-reach communities across Sierra Leone; and	7) Enriched curricula;
viii. Subsidization of fees for all public schools by the Government	8) Provision of textbooks and instructional materials;
	9) Improved funding; and
	10) Management of the entire process.

Source: Mbaga, 2021; Bello & Kamar, 2013; Elekwa, 2010

It is apparent from table 3 that the mission of FQSE slightly differs from that of UBE in that FQSE recruits additional teachers while UBE focuses on training the available teachers for the program. Both educational programs provide free education. However, only those within 3 to 18 years are strictly allowed into FQSE while only those within 6 to 15 years are allowed into UBE. Both programs ensure free meals are provided for the children to enhance their learning prowess. Both involve parents taking responsibility for the ancillary costs such as school uniforms. Both emphasize the provision of textbooks. However, in UBE, the parents pay for public examinations whereas, in FQSE, the government provides textbooks and pays for pupils taking public exams such as NPSE, BECE and WASSCE. This could make children better prepared to learn than their counterparts in the UBE program. However, UBE ensures public enlightenment and social mobilization for full community involvement, enriching the curricula and thorough management of the entire process.

Table 4: Comparison of the Aims/Objectives of FQSE and UBE

Free Quality School Education (FQSE)	Universal Basic Education (UBE)
1) to increase nation-wide access to pre-primary, primary and secondary schools as well as school level technical and vocational education and training;	i. to develop in the entire citizenry a strong consciousness for education and strong commitment to its vigorous promotion;
2) to increase access to quality education by providing a positive and conducive learning environment for school-going children under the supervision of trained and qualified teachers with adequate teaching and learning resources; and	ii. to provide free, compulsory Universal Basic Education for every Nigerian child of school age;
3) to reduce the illiteracy level especially among girls	iii. to reduce drastically the incidence of drop-out from the formal school system through improved relevance, quality and efficiency;
	iv. to cater for the learning needs of young persons who for one reason or another have had to interrupt their schooling through appropriate forms of complementary approaches to the provision and promoting of basic education; and
	v. to ensure the acquisition of the appropriate level of literacy, manipulative abilities, numeracy prowess, communicative, and life skills as well as the ethical; moral and civil values needed for laying a strong foundation for lifelong learning

Source: Ordui & Nwamadi-Wosu, 2019; Arop, Owan & Ekpang, 2018; UBEC, 2012

The objectives of UBE seem to be more than that of FQSE. This may be due to the fact that UBE is an improvement made on prior educational programs such as UPE whereas FQSE started not long ago in the year 2018 (MBBSE, 2021). The objectives are quite similar except that UBE focuses mainly on basic education, unlike FQSE which focuses on both primary and complete secondary school education. The objectives of FQSE place more emphasis on educating the female child which maybe because in time past, girls in Sierra Leone were deprived of education by their parents to stay at home to carry out domestic work (Sengeh, 2020). However, the objectives of UBE place emphasis more on drastically reducing drop-out rates of children. FQSE emphasizes more on the reduction of illiteracy levels amongst children while UBE emphasizes more on increasing numeracy, manipulation, communication and life skills as well as the literacy, ethical, moral, and civil values in the children.

Table 5: Comparison of the Goals/Components of FQSE and UBE

Free Quality School Education (FQSE)	Universal Basic Education (UBE)
i. all children will be able to complete basic education and be prepared to pursue higher education and training as appropriate needed for the workforce for national development;	i. Ensure an un-interrupted access to 9-years free and compulsory formal Universal Basic Education for every child of school age so they can contribute to national development;
ii. all children must have uninterrupted access to free quality school education in a conducive learning environment with adequate qualified teachers/learning resources;	ii. Reduce school drop-out rate and improve relevance, quality and efficiency;
iii. all children enrolled in the school system of regardless of their socio-economic status, sex, tribe, religion, physical and intellectual incapacity must be treated as one;	iii. Enable individuals acquire literacy, numeracy, and life skills for useful living;
iv. a child enrolled in school must be followed meticulously to ensure that he/she completes his/her education to at least to the basic level and can sustain his/her livelihood through employment using that basic education. This discourages drop-out rate;	iv. Provide mid-day meals to enhance children’s access, retention and completion of the school cycle;
v. education provided must have quality and relevance in modern world by using right materials, qualified teachers and government-prescribed curriculum;	v. Emphasize curriculum diversification and relevance to adequately cover individual/community needs/aspirations;
vi. education provided must have integrity that is, free from any type of fraud and malpractice	vi. Disarticulate junior secondary schools from senior secondary schools;
vii. educational system must be strengthened in the nation	vii. Realign/Integrate junior secondary education with primary education;
	viii. Individualize teaching methods;
	ix. Introduce rudiment of computer literacy;
	x. Ensure appropriate teacher professional development; and
	xi. Encourage community ownership of schools including participating in decision making process in schools

Source: MBBSE, 2021; Mbag, 2021; Onyeze, Ochiaka and Ochiaka, 2017; UBEC, 2012

The goals of both free educational programs focus on providing basic education to the children to enable them to become workforce for national development. Both programs emphasize uninterrupted access to free quality basic education and a reduction in school drop-out rates. Both programs ensure that mid-day meals are provided to enable the children to focus and retain what they learn. Both programs emphasize strengthening the system of education, and curriculum diversification, especially from the old system of education and one that is relevant to the modern world. However, a specific goal of UBE is that the curriculum should focus on the needs of the immediate community (Mbaga, 2021; Onyeze, Ochiaka & Ochiaka, 2017).

Both free educational programs also emphasize the impartation of literacy in children. However, UBE focuses also on ensuring that children have life skills for useful living in society. Both programs ensure that children regardless of their socio-economic conditions, sex, ethnicity, religion, or physical and intellectual incapacity have equal access to school. Both programs uphold - access, equity, and quality as their cardinal pursuits/goals. The goals of FQSE emphasize that the children are meticulously followed up till completion rate. However, UBE does not emphasize that the children should be watched closely till they complete the program.

However, UBE specifically emphasizes community ownership of schools whereas, in FQSE, all schools are owned, assisted, and controlled by the government. UBE emphasizes more on the professional development of teachers. Part of the UBE program is not only aimed at developing the students but also the teachers who instruct the children. FQSE emphasizes more on recruiting more teachers who are qualified. The goals of FQSE emphasizes the need for integrity such as dealing with examination mal-practices among the pupils/students. It also focuses on strengthening the entire primary and secondary school system of education in the country whereas UBE is just an improvement of the previous UPE program that was not successful. The goals of UBE place specific emphasis on computer literacy and individualized teaching methods, unlike FQSE which emphasizes the use of different teaching methods (MBBSE, 2021; Mbaga, 2021; Onyeze, Ochiaka & Ochiaka, 2017; UBE, 2012).

Table 6: Comparison of the Progress of FQSE and UBE

Free Quality School Education (FQSE)	Universal Basic Education (UBE)
i. Surge in the enrollment of pupils in schools throughout the country;	a. UNESCO's 2015 review of education in Nigeria found that enrolment at primary and junior secondary levels had greatly increased since 2000. However, transition and completion rates remained below 70%;
ii. More than 3,040 schools have been approved;	
iii. More than 1,400 teachers have been approved; 1,901 teachers re-assessed, and recruitment process for more 3,400 teachers done;	b. Enrolment rates increased by 130% for secondary education in the period from 2000 to 2013 (based on the latest available statistics from the World Bank), but decreased by 4% for primary level;
iv. More girls are enrolling in schools;	
v. Parents/guardians now relieved from the burden of school fees, buying exercise/textbooks;	c. At 2015, Nigeria ranked 103 out of 118 countries in UNESCO's
vi. Education now a right not privilege;	
vii. All children regardless of their physical, intellectual and socio-economic conditions have equal access to free quality education;	
viii. Special amenities and infrastructure	

improvements especially to physically challenged schools;	Education for All (EFA)
ix. Provision of school and furniture subsidies that enable schools to run smoothly;	Development Index, which takes into account universal primary education, adult literacy, quality of education, and gender parity;
x. Provision of school buses to address transportation disparity between the “Haves” and the “Haves Not”;	d. Seminars/workshops/short courses organized on innovative teaching techniques/instructional materials improvisation across Nigeria since inception of UBE;
xi. Children now motivated by the feeding program to stay in school instead of engaging in child labor;	e. Increase awareness of basic education;
ii. Various data collection and analyses are ongoing to understudy the issues that culminate into school dropout issues;	f. Positive refurbishments in the curriculum and personal development of thousands of teachers;
ii. Two shifts systems, After school syndicate classes and Public examination study camps have been discouraged/abolished to make students spend longer hours learning and teachers focus on teaching the right materials during normal school hours; and	g. Construction of classrooms, offices, laboratories, stores and toilets; and
v. Examination malpractices uncovered and public awareness about the need for pupils to work harder in schools.	h. Provision of learning and instructional materials like exercise books, textbooks and teaching aids.

Source: MBBSE, 2021; Amuchie, Asotibe & Audu, 2015; UBEC, 2012

Free education in Sierra Leone and Nigeria has both recorded a huge increase in pupil/students' enrollment including an increase in girls' enrollment. The two countries have recorded progress in areas of provision and construction of infrastructures such as classrooms, offices, laboratories, stores, and toilets. Both programs have made progress in the area of provision of learning/instructional materials such as exercise books and textbooks. They equally have made progress in motivating children to learn through their feeding programs. Free educational programs in the two countries have made progress in relieving parents/guardians from the burden of school fees and buying exercise/textbooks. Both programs have increased awareness of basic education in different nations. Both programs have recorded the training and thousands of teachers for dissemination of knowledge to the children.

There has been somewhat increase in completion rates among the children in the two countries. They have both significant progress in ensuring that children are not discriminated against regardless of their tribe, religion, gender etcetera but are allowed equal rights and access to free school education. However, UBE in Nigeria has improved on its rank in providing education for all. It has made significant positive refurbishments in the curriculum in Nigeria primary and junior secondary education. Successful seminars/workshops/short courses have been organized on innovative teaching techniques/instructional materials improvisation for teachers and skill development for students across Nigeria since the inception of UBE.

FQSE on the other hand have made significant progress in educating the physically challenged children in the nation, especially in the provision of special amenities and

infrastructure improvements. FQSE has also ensured that free transportation is provided for the children, unlike UBE. FQSE have made progress in ensuring that examination malpractices are uncovered. FQSE have also ensured that the 'two shifts systems', 'after school syndicate classes' and 'public examination study camps' have been discouraged/abolished to make students spend longer hours learning while teachers focus on teaching the right materials during normal school hours.

Table 7: Comparison of the Challenges of FQSE and UBE

Free Quality School Education (FQSE)	Universal Basic Education (UBE)
i. Inadequate financial resources, which have been the major challenge. There is a huge financial gap between the needs and implementation through the FQSE program;	a. Serious problems in the course contents and the approach adopted in its implementation;
ii. Increase in school entrants has compounded infrastructure to cope with the current enrollment and attendance. For instance, some schools lack sitting accommodation due to the high enrollment rate;	b. Implementation of the program is often half-hearted;
iii. Unavailability of accurate, timely, and updated data which leads to delays in funding, planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation;	c. Problem of qualified teachers;
iv. Inadequate infrastructure poses a threat in the delivery and implementation. An increase in enrollment and attendance naturally brings about overcrowding. Most schools lack the needed accommodation, facilities, and furniture to match the current registration;	d. Inadequate funding has continued to hinder effective implementation of the scheme in many parts of the country
v. Inadequately trained teachers as the number of qualified teachers cannot meet the current influx of teacher's pupil ratio (1:45)	e. Inadequate data for planning is a major setback facing the UBE program. Inadequate and poor data pose planning difficulties and implementation challenges;
vi. Lack of a distinct curriculum structure/approach. This undoubtedly create gaps, tensions, and confusion in the implementation process because the new system will be implemented using the old system approach	f. Poor management of available resources and corruption
vii. Need to satisfy teachers in order to keep the completion, quality and relevance and integrity components of the FQSE working for the children	g. The quality of the national school curriculum is undermined by the generally low quality of teachers who implement it, which translates into low levels of learning achievement;
viii. Need for the construction of more schools across the country;	h. Infrastructure, toilets and furniture are inadequate and in a dilapidated state;
ix. The old system still undermines the flagship program of the President either by slowing down processes, putting bureaucratic bottlenecks in the path of progress	i. The system of collecting comprehensive, relevant data for planning is weak;
	j. social and cultural barriers that are hindering female participation;
	k. lack of enforcement of the UBE Act 2004 on enrolment and retention;
	l. population explosion leading to severe increase in class size.

Source: Mbaga, 2021; Amuchie et al., 2015; Bello & Kamar, 2013; Anaduaka & Okafor, 2013

Despite the progress made by both programs, they are faced with several challenges. Both programs are faced with similar challenges such as inadequate funding or finances, inability to cater for increased enrollment of pupils/students in terms of infrastructures caused by population explosion, and unavailability of accurate, timely, and updated data or inadequate data for planning which leads to delays in funding, planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation. Both programs are also faced with bureaucratic bottlenecks that tend to undermine the program or who are half-hearted towards the progress of the program. Both face the issue of the inadequate number of qualified teachers to meet up with the increased enrollment of pupils/students. Both programs are also challenged by inadequate infrastructure for the students. In Nigeria, there are either dilapidated or unavailable infrastructures.

Both programs also face the issue of the quality of distinct curriculum structure/approaches for their implementation. They are also challenged with the need to keep their teachers by ensuring they are regularly well-paid and compensated. However, they differ in a few challenges. The UBE faces the issue of poor management of available resources and corruption which of course seems to be rampant in the nation. The multi-ethnic diversity in Nigeria also poses a major challenge to UBE in that it poses social and cultural barriers that do hinder females' participation in the program. UBE also faces the challenge of lack of enforcement of the UBE Act 2004 on enrolment and retention. However, FQSE faces the challenge of the need to construct more schools across the country unlike Nigeria which already has many public schools that just need innovation.

5. Conclusion

This paper examined the free education programs in Sub Sahara Africa: A comparative analysis of Universal Basic Education (UBE) in Nigeria and Free Quality School Education (FQSE) in Sierra Leone. It is revealed that in a bid to achieve education for all, both Nigeria and Sierra Leone began free education program that offers at least basic education to the children in a bid to reduce illiteracy rates, reducing drop-out rates, improving their skills for useful living, empowering them to become workforce thus contributing to national development. UBE and FQSE were started on different dates by the federal government of both nations. Both programs (UBE and FQSE) have vision, mission, scope, duration, goals and objectives which are quite similar in some aspects to one another while differing in other aspects. However, the paper has shown that despite the progress recorded in the realization of the vision, mission, goals and objectives, the programs (UBE and FQSE) are still faced with myriad of similar and contrasting challenges that tend to hamper their successful implementation and progress.

6. Recommendations

- 1) In terms of duration, the FQSE program extends beyond junior secondary school. It is therefore recommended that the UBE program should also imbibe this duration as well by providing free education for students up to the secondary school level;
- 2) The FQSE program also takes care of public examinations of the students such as NPSE, BECE and WASSCE, the UBE program should also ensure that they take care of the public examinations of the pupils/students such as Junior WAEC and SSCE;
- 3) In FQSE, there is a provision of school-level technical and vocational education and training while in UBE, there is a provision of non-formal education for school drop-outs. Both programs can include what is missing from their scope;

- 4) Since both programs face the issue of financing/funding, they should do all they can to solicit funds from both national and international avenues to ensure the successful implementation of the program;
- 5) Both programs face the issue of inadequate infrastructure and qualified teachers. The government should do more in ensuring that more infrastructures are constructed like the FQSE is doing or innovated like the UBE to ensure a better teacher-to-student ratio. In so doing, children will learn better; and
- 6) Both programs seem to face the challenge of management and inaccurate data collection for the efficient planning of the program. The government could also take a step further in ensuring that managers are properly screened before giving the duty of managing the programs. Also, those in charge of collecting reliable data should be properly monitored so that they do their job well in ensuring adequate and reliable data are provided for efficient planning of the programs.

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